

SPIRITUAL RISE - OF THE THIRD RENAISSANCE
SOLID FOUNDATION

Sardor Shamsidinov

Samarkand state University researcher

Great thinker Alisher Navoiy addressed us and said, "You are such a society build so that intelligence will improve the face of the Motherland doer, moral education to the people of the society let it become a force that gives joy and pride on the basis of solidarity." like saying. "The body of the life of the society" of the head of our state if there is an economy, its soul and spirit is spirituality The breath of awakening in essence is essentially to the calls of Navoi in harmony, the foundation of the Third Renaissance Education is good for our people, who are determined to create behavior, intelligence, knowledge, spirituality, what an incomparable power and spiritual resource once again meant that. So, a society with high spirituality The body of the economy, which is the body of his life, has a soul and a soul life, an incomparable creative power is granted.

Because spirituality and enlightenment are an unparalleled power in all times, happiness, peace, creativity, harmony criterion, spiritual purification and has been a boon that uplifts the soul. Because it is the nation, the people, that is, the moral that leads people to high qualities and perfection He urged us to live according to the standards, not to become a prisoner of selfishness and ignorance, but to always be awake in the path of goodness, to improve this world, and to beautify it. But today, we are increasingly concerned about the threats aimed at derailing the spiritual and spiritual world of our dear children, who have been polished, enriched and developed for thousands of years, overshadowing our eternal values and moral qualities. So to speak, the struggle between good and evil, constructive and destructive forces, and ideas is becoming more and more obvious.

Evil, selfishness, immorality, corruption in the hearts of people when will the seed of evil and ignorance be destroyed? Kindness, what is the power of enlightenment? Of course, first with good intentions, good from word, good deed, towards pure and noble goals from national unity. It is clear from the experience of the ancestors which country is their own to the path leading to the goal of the national will by concentrating the power of the people if he can start, if he can direct the potential of the nation correctly, he the position of the state, a source of trust, becomes an unequaled creative force.

Now, "The system of spiritual and educational affairs has been completely overhauled

as stated in the decision on improvement measures, Our people, especially the youth, are relentless in their pursuit of ignorance To start organizational and scientific-research work on protection against decaying spiritual threats based on new requirements, in this direction, state organizations, civil society institutions, mass media and private sector social will raise the work on strengthening cooperation to a new level.

Poet and writer, journalist, on creative and cultural issues involving scientists in educational institutions due to the introduction of the position of propagandist inculcating the "Lesson of Patriotism" into the hearts of millions of students a new spiritual and creative spirit enters. State higher education institutions and their branches, regardless of the number of students, vice-rector for youth issues and spiritual and educational affairs the introduction of the post of spiritual and educational work in the higher education system takes it to a new level. With this decision, in general terms Spirituality and enlightenment in all districts and cities of our country white blessing is being given to the establishment of their residences.

The more perfect the education, the happier the people will live. Education is the basis of spirituality. "How much education if it is perfect, the people will live so happily," he says sages. In order for education to be perfect, it is impossible to allow a gap in this matter. We all know that nowadays in our country, great importance is attached to raising the level of reading and raising the culture of reading. Many of our children are acquiring modern knowledge through books and the Internet, while many young people are moving away from books and spending their precious time on social networks.

It is the will of the heart that brings the third awakening breath The head of our state with these historic decisions to us great goals is calling. This is not just a call, this is the Third Awakening the desire of the heart that breathes, whispering in our veins standing ancestors. We are capable of great deeds, high spirituality and on the basis of morality, human qualities are the priority, humanity, goodness We are a nation that deserves to live in a prosperous society, a great country based on its ideology.

It can be said that millions of young people are the most priceless inheritance from our ancestors, which nothing can replace. his life among the countries of the world the ground for them to live equally and proudly with their style and progress opens the way to spiritual perfection. Spirituality, high morals, spiritual purity, heart wakefulness, awake conscience, strong faith are like the breath of spring. As far as the influence of his farakhash breath is present, unfortunately for him there are so many counter-cold winds. That is why he always, in every period, is stronger than threats and is full of power. Because give him the awakening of the times The good deeds of those who do it give strength. May the spring of spirituality be blessed to all of us!

